

ON SOME LANDSNAILS COLLECTED IN SINTRA.**Stefano Palazzi*****Preface**

On August 15, 1986, I had the opportunity to collect some landsnails in Sintra, among which some interesting small ones, so that I was compelled to list them for permanent record. The eighteen species were picked up in Castelo dos Mouros hill, the majority of the species lying in leafmould or in rock crevices litter. In the following list I constantly refer to NOBRE's book of 1941, whenever possible, for iconographical and bibliographical references; numbers in brackets indicate the quantity of shells found.

LIST OF SPECIES**POMATIIDAE**

Pomatias elegans (Müller, 1774). NOBRE, p. 224. (1).

ELLOBIIDAE

Carychium minimum gracile (Morelet, 1845). NOBRE, p. 175. (43). The external shell morphology reminds much *C. tridentatum* (Risso, 1826), being it tall and strongly growth-lined; columellar plica, however, is untwisted as in typical *minimum* (see illustration).

PYRAMIDULIDAE

Pyramidula rupestris (Draparnaud, 1801). NOBRE, p. 80. (7).

PUPILLIDAE

Lauria cylindracea (Da Costa, 1778). NOBRE, p. 144. (7).

Leiostyla anglica (W. Wood, 1828). NOBRE, p. 148. (23).

VALLONIIDAE

Acanthinula aculeata (Müller, 1774). NOBRE, p. 81. (2).

Spermodea lamellata (Jeffreys, 1830). Not listed by NOBRE; possibly new for Portuguese fauna. (3). This delightfully sculptured little shell is adequately described by CAMERON & KERNEY (1979:98).

Planogyra sororcula (Benoit, 1857). Not listed by NOBRE; possibly new to Portugal. (3). See CAMERON & KERNEY (1979:98).

ZONITIDAE

Aegopinella pura (Alder, 1830). Not in NOBRE's book; possibly mistaken with *Vitrea crystallina* (Müller, 1774). (2). See CAMERON & KERNEY (1979:120).

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- Oxychilus cellarius* (Müller, 1774). NOBRE, p. 53. (31).
Zonitoides excavatus (Alder, 1830). Not listed by NOBRE; possibly new to Portugal. (1). See CAMERON & KERNEY (1979:127).

CLAUSILIIDAE

- Clausilia bidentata rugosa* (Draparnaud, 1801). NOBRE, p. 156. (14).
Balea perversa (Linnaeus, 1758) NOBRE, p. 159. (2).

HELICIDAE

- Candidula intersecta* (Poiret, 1801). NOBRE, p. 103. (1).
Oestophora lusitanica (L. Pfeiffer, 1841). NOBRE, p. 83. (19).
Oestophora barbula (Rossmässler 1836). NOBRE, p. 86. (5).
Theba pisana (Müller, 1774). NOBRE, p. 91. (1).
Cepaea nemoralis (Linnaeus, 1758). NOBRE, p. 128. (7).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

PEDRO CALLAPEZ TONICHER helped me so much in the field as did LUIS PISANI BURNAY in literature search. To both are addressed my sincere thanks.

RESUMO

O autor estuda a fauna de moluscos terrestres de Sintra (18 espécies).

LITERATURE CITED

- CAMERON, R. A. D. & KERNEY, M. P. (1979) — A field guide to the land snails of Britain and North-West Europe. Glasgow, Collins & Co., 1-288, pls. 1-24.
NOBRE, A. (1941) — Fauna malacologica de Portugal. II. Moluscos terrestres efluviiais. — *Mém. Est. Mus. Zool. Univ. Coimbra* 124: 1-279, pls. 1-30.

**Carychium minimum gracile* (MORELET, 1845). Sintra, 15.VIII. 1986, in leafmould at Castelo dos Mouros hill. Shell broken to show inner columellar plica. SEM photo, 49.4 x.

